

A novel soluble and conducting polyaniline

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A soluble conducting polyaniline containing no substituent on the aromatic ring has been synthesized by incorporation of the novel, versatile di(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate dopant anion which makes the polyaniline highly soluble in polar, weakly polar and some non polar solvents. The M_w value is 26160 and the solubility (extractability) in TMU and in dichloromethane are 85 and 35% respectively. The electrical conductivity of the dry solid is 5×10^{-3} S/cm. The dopant ratio is 4 : 1.5 as N : S. The TGA shows that the removal of water which is ~4.54% is completed by about 215° and that decomposition i.e. removal of the dopant starts just after that and is completed by ~305°. The polymer shows solvatochromism.

Out of the three main classes of conducting polymers polyaniline, polythiophene and polypyrrole, only polyaniline is stable in the acidic medium and hence environmentally stable. All these three polymers are insoluble in organic solvents and water and hence non-processible. Polyaniline base is soluble in organic solvents but non-conducting and polyaniline salt is conducting but insoluble. Combining both the properties of electrical conductivity and solubility constitutes an important achievement, for it will allow the formation of fiber forming conducting material. Conducting polymers, unlike conventional polymers, being thermally unstable, are not melt processible.

It is well known that the presence of plasticizers increases the solubility of polymers. A few years back a soluble polypyrrole¹ was synthesized using pyrrole monomer (no substitution in the ring) but with an anionic surfactant working as dopant, dodecylbenzenesulfonic acid [DBSA], with a little improved solubility in organic solvents like *m*-cresol, chloroform, DMF, DMSO etc. presumably due to the increased overall interaction of the solvent with the surfactant anion. The addition of excess surfactant improved the solubility especially in weakly polar solvents. Viscosity studies showed that the molecular weight was low. Generally the larger the amount of the plasticizer, the greater is the solubility but excess of the plasticizer which is an insulator decreases its conductivity.

Recently MacDiarmid *et al.*² synthesized a polypyrrole using a substituent free pyrrole monomer but with a dopant, di(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate. The resulting polymer was quite soluble in many organic solvents like DMSO, DMF, NMP, *m*-cresol, *o*-chlorophenol, dichloromethane, chloro-

form, benzene, trichloroacetic acid, acetic acid and formic acid. The conductivity of the films made from DMSO and DMF solutions is about 3 and 2.3 S/cm respectively. The molecular chain had about 303 pyrrole units ($M_w = 62296$ and $M_n = 33337$). This was a remarkable achievement.

We report herein, the synthesis of a polyaniline with the dopant di(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinate and its characterization with elemental analyses TGA, conductivity measurement, molecular weight determination, solubilities (extractabilities) in polar, weakly polar and nonpolar solvents, IR and UV-Vis spectral data and open circuit voltage of the polymer versus pH.

Results and discussion

The elemental analyses show that the polymer even on drying on the vacuum line for a long time still has water. Using the values from analysis and the TGA one can easily find that the ratio between the emeraldine and the DEHSS is 1.5 DEHSS per four ring segment. Thermogravimetric analysis shows elimination of 4.54% water which is tantamount to having 2.63 H₂O in the formula of the polymer. It seems that the polymer starts losing the dopant from here onwards and is completed by ~305° (obs. wt. loss for 2.63 H₂O and 1.5 DEHSS = 61.6%, calcd. wt. loss = 60.7%). The residue left at 1000° is ~15% which may be due to carbon ash left after complete decomposition which is quite understandable in the absence of oxygen.

The electrical conductivity of the polymer is not very high but it may be reasonably high in the form of a film and especially in the form of a stretched film.

The molecular weights are $M_n = 3757$, $M_w = 26159$, $M_p = 17400$ and the PDI = 6.96. So the molecular weight is not

very high as compared with that of Emeraldine salt (corresponding with that of the Emeraldine base form), but are very high in comparison with the polymethyl-, polypropyl- and polymethoxy aniline ($M_w = 7164, 5253$ and 13247 respectively)³.

The extractibility is very high in polar solvents and especially in TMU where it is ~85%. It is 25 and 35% in chloroform and dichloromethane respectively.

The IR spectra are devoid of sharp peaks as is found in Emeraldine hydrochloride. The tilted base line is indicative of free carrier absorption. The electronic effect⁴ obscures most important information above 2000 cm^{-1} . The absence of absorption at 750 cm^{-1} eliminates the possibility of 1,2 substitution and the absence of absorptions in the region of $750\text{--}780$ and $650\text{--}710\text{ cm}^{-1}$, shows the absence of 1,3 substitution. The band at 730 cm^{-1} with shoulders is characteristic of a 1,4-disubstituted phenyl ring. The presence of these absorptions and the absence of bands indicating a form of monosubstituted phenyl ring suggests that the polymer is quite long in comparison with polyparaphenylene which has noticeable end group absorbances in the $600\text{--}760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region⁵. A band at 1170 cm^{-1} corresponds to the polymer backbone, 1300 cm^{-1} shows for CH bands. There is also a weak absorption at 3390 cm^{-1} for secondary amine. The intensity of the free carrier tail ($\sim 1500\text{ nm}$) in doped polyaniline has been taken as a qualitative measure of the carrier mobility in the chain⁶. This is not intense in Eme.DEHSS and correspondingly the conductivity has been found to be low. The peaks at 1500 and 1600 cm^{-1} are of low intensity but sharper than those found in polyaniline hydrochloride. This shows that probably Eme.DEHSS is in a somewhat low oxidation state (less quinonoid than benzenoid rings) than Emeraldine hydrochloride. Heeger *et al.*⁷ on the basis of these absorptions observed that polyaniline hydrochloride is more oxidized than polyparaphenyleneamineimine hydrochloride. This is also evident from low value of conductivity in Eme.DEHSS but it may partly be due to interchain distance in Eme.DEHSS because of the bulky dopant, DEHSS. DEHSSNa shows absorptions at $812, 1167, 1300, 1419, 1580$ and 2315 cm^{-1} . Some of these are seen in the polymer.

The Eme.DEHSS shows blue and green colors in different solvents with the same concentration of the polymer. The absorption occurring between 332 and 346 nm in different solvents is a band gap transition from valence band to the conduction band (Table 1). This is very clear cut in the solvents DMF, NMP and TMU. In CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2 , *m*-cresol and THF there is a plateau spanning the region ~ 1 eV to 454 nm . The band gap energy goes up slightly in coordinating solvents on aging. No such trend is observed in non-coordinating solvents. The bands at $809, 807$ and 875 nm in chloroform, dichloromethane and *m*-cresol and at $632, 641$,

$644, 798$ and 636 nm in the coordinating solvents – DMF, DMSO, NMP, THF, TMU – are exciton (charge transfer between benzenoid and quinonoid) bands. This band goes up in energy in all solvents on aging. The polymers change from the rod to coil like form with time. It has been shown earlier that the Emeraldine base form shows only two bands in the UV-Vis region whereas the salt form shows three bands⁸. This is perhaps due to a band in the band gap region.

Table 1. UV-Vis spectra of the polyaniline in different organic solvents

Solvent	Polymer	λ_{nm} (A)		
CHCl_3	Fresh	346 (0.60) ^a	429 (0.52) ^a	809 (1.1) ^b
		346 (1.8) ^a	418 (1.7) ^a	805 (3.5) ^b
	aged	350 (0.60) ^a	433 (0.52) ^a	790 (1.3) ^b
		351 (1.8) ^a	424 (1.7) ^a	801 (3.7) ^b
CH_2Cl_2	Fresh	345 (0.55) ^a	429 (0.52) ^a	807 (1.1) ^b
		351 (2.2) ^a	425 (2.0) ^a	798 (4.5) ^b
	aged	342 (0.55) ^a	433 (0.50) ^a	791 (1.3) ^b
		351 (2.3) ^a	424 (2.0) ^a	776 (4.3) ^b
<i>m</i> -Cresol	Fresh	342 (0.62) ^a	430 (0.62) ^a	875 (1.0) ^b
			444 (1.2) ^a	
	aged	342 (0.60) ^a	425 (0.60) ^a	867 (0.93) ^b
			443 (1.5) ^a	
DMF	Fresh	336 (1.1) ^b		632 (0.70) ^b
		332 (2.3) ^b		621 (1.5) ^b
	aged	333 (1.0) ^b		625 (0.78) ^b
		332 (2.3) ^b		631 (1.4) ^b
DMSO	Fresh	337 (0.91)	454 (0.34)	641 (trace) ^c
		335 (1.1)	443 (0.49)	
	aged	334 (1.0)	446 (0.23)	641 (trace) ^c
		334 (1.2)	440 (0.28)	
NMP	Fresh	338 (1.1)		644 (0.81)
		336 (4.8)	447 (1.8)	661 (1.9)
	aged	335 (1.2)		643 (0.81)
		362 (3.0)	454 (1.1)	680 (2.0)
THF	Fresh	346 (0.60) ^a	424 (0.55) ^a	798 (1.2)
		346 (0.85) ^a	433 (0.70) ^a	790 (1.8)
	aged	336 (0.57) ^a	434 (0.42) ^a	778 (1.0)
		346 (0.86) ^a	431 (0.64) ^a	773 (1.6)
TMU	Fresh	336 (1.1)		636 (0.81)
		334 (3.0)		635 (1.9)
	aged	332 (1.1)		635 (0.91)
		334 (3.0)		634 (1.9)

The values given in italics are for solutions of the polymer in pure solvent.

^aplateau, ^bdistinct, ^cflat.

Fig. 1. Potential vs pH Eme.DEHSS solid.

The potential of the Eme.DEHSS soluble portion is 0.388 and that of the solid is 0.332 V at pH 0.30. It increases up to about 0.5 V and then starts decreasing till by about pH 13 it becomes -0.147 and -0.153 V vs SCE. It seems that at a pH of about 9 detachment of the dopant begins and onset of hydrolysis takes place. There is a quick potential drop at pH 11.5 (see Fig. 1).

Experimental

Aniline (Aldrich Chemicals) (20.0 ml, 0.219 mol) was cooled and added to cooled 1 L soluble of di(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinic acid sodium salt (DEHSSNa, 22.2 g, 0.05 mol) in water. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (41.7 ml) was added to the mixture, cooled to 0° and stirred constantly. Ammonium peroxydisulfate (11.5 g, 0.05 mol) was dissolved in 100 ml of water, cooled to 0° and mixed with the mixture. This mixture was stirred for ~4 h and the temperature was maintained at 0° when a green precipitate was formed and was separated by vacuum filtration. Finally the whole precipitate was transferred on to the funnel. The precipitate was washed 2 times with 250 ml water. The precipitate was placed in 1 L water and stirred for 5 h and filtered again. This process was repeated once more and finally it was washed with four installments of 250 ml water. The precipitate was dried in a desiccator and then on a vacuum line at a pressure of 10⁻⁴ mm for 3 days. The weight of the dry sample was 13.5 g. An attempt to synthesize this product without the use of HCl but using di(2-ethylhexyl)sulfosuccinic acid (DEHSSNa treated with a cation exchange resin) failed showing that the presence of protons in good quantity is necessary for the formation of Emeraldine.

The polymer was subjected to elemental analysis for carbon, hydrogen, chlorine, nitrogen and sulfur. There was no chlorine in the polymer (Found : C, 62.76; H, 7.77; N, 5.39; S, 4.66. Calcd. for Emeraldine + 1.5 DEHSS + 2.63 H₂O : C, 62.23; H, 7.62; N, 5.38; S, 4.62%).

The thermogram was recorded at a scan rate of 20° per minute between ambient and 1000° in nitrogen atmosphere.

The conductivity of the doped polymer was determined by the four probe technique using a pellet. The conductivity is 5 × 10⁻³ S/cm.

The molecular weights were determined using gel permeation technique in TMU.

The extractibilities were determined by mixing 0.2 g of the solid polymer in 10 ml of the organic solvent, stirring for 6 × h, filtering through a filter paper into a preweighed petri-dish, drying the petri-dish in an oven at 100° and weighing the dried polymer. The solubilities were determined with the same method except 0.5 g of the solid polymer was mixed with 5.00 ml of the solvent.

Solvent	Extractibility in g dissolved polymer/100 g polymer (%)	Solubility g polymer/100 ml solvent
Chloroform	25	20
Dichloromethane	35	46
<i>m</i> -Cresol	~0	6
Dimethylformamide (DMF)	50	53
Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO)	20	21
<i>N</i> -Methylpyrrolidinone (NMP)	40	67
Tetrahydrofuran (THF)	30	78
Tetramethylurea (TMU)	85	78

The IR spectra of the polymer were recorded in KBr pellet using KBr pellet of DEHSSNa as a reference and the spectra of DEHSSNa was also recorded in KBr pellet.

The UV-Vis spectra were recorded on Cary 30BIO UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The polymer was dissolved in dichloromethane to make the most concentrated solution. 1.00 ml of this solution was placed in a 50.00 ml volumetric flask and the solution was made up to the mark with the proper solvent. This mixture of 1 ml of dichloromethane and ~49 ml of the proper solvent was used as a solvent. The spectra were recorded between 190 and 900 nm. Spectra were also recorded in pure solvents so that the concentrations remain more or less the same.

The polymer was dissolved in TMU and the solution was placed on a platinum foil and dried in an oven at 100°. The platinum was used as a working electrode dipped in a solution of HCl and the potential measured versus a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The pH was determined with a pH meter and the pH was varied with the addition of 0.01 to 2 M sodium hydroxide.

References

1. D. Y. Kim, J. Y. Lee, C. Y. Kim, E. T. Kang and K. L. Tan, *Synth. Met.*, 1995, **72**, 243; J. Y. Lee, D. Y. Kim and C. Y. Kim, *Synth. Met.*, 1995, **74**, 103.
2. E. J. Oh, K. S. Jang and A. G. MacDiarmid, *Synth. Met.*, 2002, **125**, 267.
3. N. Ahmad, P. Feng, H. Schursky, S. Shah, D. Antonacci, M. B. Cichowicz and A. G. MacDiarmid, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 673.
4. S. Yaniger and D. W. Vidrine, a private communication.
5. D. Dolphin and A. Wick, "Tabulation of Infrared Data", Wiley, New York, 1997.
6. P.-C. Wang and A. G. MacDiarmid, *Synth. Met.*, 2001, **119**, 367.
7. F. Wudl, R. O. Angus (Jr.), F. L. Lu, P. M. Allemand, D. J. Vachon, M. Nowak, Z. X. Liu and A. J. Heeger, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1987, **109**, 3686.
8. N. Ahmad, P. Feng, H. Schursky and S. Shah, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1993, **32**, 679.